

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Modified Sunflower Optimization Algorithm for Task Scheduling in Cloud Computing

 OPEN ACCESS

Received: 22/03/2025

Accepted: 21/04/2025

Published: 11/05/2025

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Citation: Mary JM, Amalarethinam DIG (2025) Modified Sunflower Optimization Algorithm for Task Scheduling in Cloud Computing. Indian Journal of Science and Technology 18(17): 1365-1376. <https://doi.org/10.17485/IJST/V18i17.537>

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Funding: None

Competing Interests: None

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Published By Indian Society for Education and Environment ([iSee](https://www.indjst.org/))

ISSN

Print: 0974-6846

Electronic: 0974-5645

Abstract

Objective: To develop a task scheduling algorithm that efficiently approximates solutions for the multi-objective task scheduling problem in a cloud environment, optimizing resource utilization, execution time, cost, and overall system performance. **Method:** A Modified Sunflower Optimization Algorithm for Task Scheduling (MSOTS) is proposed to improve efficiency in cloud environments. The traditional sunflower optimization algorithm is enhanced with Levy flight, crossover, and mutation operations to achieve a better balance between exploration and exploitation while preventing entrapment in local minima. These enhancements help improve convergence speed and solution quality. CloudSim is utilized for comprehensive performance evaluation, comparing MSOTS with existing algorithms in terms of execution time, cost, and resource utilization. The randomly generated dataset (500 tasks and 50 VMs) is used to analyze the performance of the MSOTS. **Findings:** The results demonstrate that MSOA significantly reduces makespan and cost while enhancing resource utilization. Specifically, the proposed method reduces makespan by 22.43% compared to PSO and 14.95% compared to SOA. Additionally, cost is reduced by 14.47% and 10.38% compared to PSO and SOA, respectively, while resource utilization increases by 3.89% and 2.51% over these methods. These findings indicate that MSOA effectively improves task scheduling performance in terms of makespan, cost efficiency, and resource utilization, making it a promising approach for cloud computing environments. **Novelty:** The MSOA is integrated with single-point crossover, swap mutation, and Lévy flight to update the solution, which prevents entrapment in local minima and premature convergence and enhances task scheduling efficiency, optimizes resource allocation, minimizes execution time, and reduces overall costs in cloud computing environments.

Keywords: Meta-heuristic; Sunflower optimization; Levy flight; Crossover; Mutation

1 Introduction

Cloud computing offers various services on a pay-per-use model to customers and apps by leveraging its compute, storage, and bandwidth capabilities⁽¹⁾. The diverse cloud attributes, including on-demand access, self-service capabilities, quality of service, virtualization, and flexibility, contribute to the cloud's popularity in both industrial and research sectors. Moreover, Cloud Computing offers a superior option for data and infrastructure management⁽²⁾.

The extensive adoption of cloud computing across various domains presents numerous issues, including load balancing, energy usage, safety and task scheduling. Task scheduling is considered as a significant challenge in the cloud computing environment. It denotes the allocation of application tasks to accessible resources in the cloud as virtual machines (VMs). Given the restricted number of VMs with varying capabilities, an effective scheduling approach is essential for the precise allocation of application activities to these VMs⁽³⁾.

Task scheduling is essential in the resource management system of cloud computing, ensuring the attainment of user Quality of Service (QoS) performance in areas such as Makespan and throughput, among others⁽⁴⁾. Furthermore, excellent task scheduling significantly reduces operational expenses for cloud service providers, especially regarding energy usage and resource utilization. The majority of academics are driven to build suitable scheduling algorithms to find rapid and efficient solutions to the issues of task scheduling in cloud computing⁽⁵⁾.

Task scheduling issues can be solved through heuristic and meta-heuristic methods. Heuristic based solutions are suited for individual issues and give optimal outcomes; nevertheless, for NP-hard problems, their efficacy is restricted to below a particular level. Several heuristic strategies exist which includes Min-Min, Max-Min, First Come First Serve, Shortest Job First, and Round Robin etc.⁽⁶⁾. Meta-heuristics are overarching tactics intended to enhance and direct the search process for identifying optimal solutions in intricate optimization challenges⁽⁷⁾. Meta-heuristic scheduling approaches are meant to identify near-optimal solutions to NP-hard problems with low complexity, making them particularly useful for scheduling tasks. These algorithms yield a satisfactory result in a timely manner through the utilization of random search capabilities⁽⁸⁾. Genetic⁽⁹⁾, Particle swarm optimization⁽¹⁰⁾, Gray wolf optimization⁽¹¹⁾, Ant colony optimization⁽¹²⁾ and Sunflower optimization⁽¹³⁾ are some of the meta-heuristic scheduling algorithms. Most meta-heuristic-based approaches yield promising outcomes; yet they are prone to entrapment in local optima, and their efficacy remains suboptimal.

Table 1 shows the summary of existing literature. It includes methodology, contribution, limitation or research gap. To over the limitations of existing approach this research introduces a modified sunflower optimization strategy for task scheduling (MSOTS) to enhance the performance of meta-heuristic-based scheduling. The conventional sunflower optimization technique is enhanced with the incorporation of operations like as Lévy flight, crossover, and mutation. It can balance the growth and intensification processes of the proposed strategy and avert trapping in local minima. The main significance of this research work outlined below.

- Formulate a scheduling strategy to reduce expenses, minimize makespan, and improve resource utilization.
- Develop a task scheduling algorithm based on meta-heuristic methods for the cloud environment.
- Formulate a modified sunflower optimization algorithm including diverse operations to address the multi-objective task scheduling dilemma.
- Assess the efficacy of the proposed work through simulation and analyze and discuss the simulation results.

2 Methodology

A cloud data center comprises numerous host machines that offer diverse resources to end customers. Each host machine typically accommodates thousands of rapidly created virtual machines. Cloud companies offer diverse virtual machines with varying performance and cost characteristics. This study discusses the assignment of virtual machines to incoming autonomous tasks. It is presumed that each task will operate on a singular virtual machine and is indivisible. Task scheduling utilizing heterogeneous resources constitutes a combinatorial optimization problem, which can be delineated as follows:

Let consider $V = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_m\}$, where V is a set of virtual machines (VMs) and m represents the total number of VMs within the cloud. Each virtual machine possesses distinct resources (e.g., MIPS) and associated costs.

Let consider $T = \{t_1, t_2, t_3, \dots, t_n\}$, where T is the set of assigned tasks, and n represents the number of independent tasks executed on the virtual machines (m). Each task includes the number of instructions. The quantity of tasks exceeds the quantity of virtual machines. The sets T and VM function as inputs for a scheduling algorithm, and an efficient allocation of all tasks across a collection of VMs yields a final solution aimed at minimizing makespan, cost, and maximize the resource utilization.

This study presents a task scheduling technique for cloud computing that employs multi-objective scheduling conditions to enhance schedule optimization efficiency. The predominant evaluation criteria include cost, energy usage, task completion duration, revenue makespan, and availability⁽²⁰⁾. The suggested method assesses suitable conditions based on cost, resource

Table 1. Summary of Existing Literature

Ref.	Methodology	Contributions	Limitations/ Research Gap
(10)	Adaptive Particle Swarm Optimisation based task scheduling	An adjustable inertia weight method was incorporated into the Particle Swarm Optimization for task scheduling.	Insufficient applicability across various cloud environments. It disregards the cost factor.
(13)	Enhanced sunflower optimization	This method involved the creation of a novel pollination strategy to improve the discovery and extraction abilities for navigating the solution space. The method determined the best possible task scheduling issue with polynomial time difficulty.	The methodology was evaluated solely on a restricted set of parameters (makespan and energy), neglecting the assessment of additional parameters (cost and resource consumption) to demonstrate the model's efficiency.
(14)	Artificial Bee Colony Algorithm with a Q-learning	A multi-objective scheduling method to enhance task scheduling with a reinforcement learning strategy that accelerates the performance of the ABC algorithm.	Performance challenges in intricate, dynamic task scheduling.
(15)	Hybrid gray wolf optimization and genetic algorithm	Implementing mutation and crossover to maintain wolf variety and enhance local search inside the algorithm. A novel fitness function is introduced that simultaneously addresses numerous objectives.	The scheduling of larger tasks is inadequately addressed.
(16)	Discrete Tuna Swarm Optimization for Task Scheduling	New operators are implemented to modify the position of particles. This alteration enables the algorithm to preserve its stochastic characteristics while operating with discrete numbers.	The discourse on computational complexity is inadequate. Scalability concerns arise when performance is evaluated with an increased number of tasks and resources.
(17)	Chameleon and Remora Search Optimization Algorithm	This solution integrates the qualities of Chameleon Search Algorithm and Remora Search Optimization Algorithm utilizing a greedy approach for mimicking the real cloud computing work scheduling process.	Execution time and other performance parameters that are poorly attained while taking into account big real-world instances.
(18)	Hybrid of Ant colony and particle swarm optimization	This methodology integrates Ant Colony Optimization and Particle Swarm Optimization. Particle Swarm Optimization was employed for global search, whereas Ant Colony Optimization was utilized for local search.	The time complexity is increased.
(19)	Opposition based sunflower optimization	This method introduces a novel pollination mechanism to improve both discovery and extraction capabilities.	Extending the duration for execution.

usage, and makespan to facilitate effective scheduling. Scheduling inside a cloud computing environment necessitates the construction of a fitness function to yield optimal solutions while simultaneously addressing the multi-objective approach to derive the answer. This paper employed a weighted sum technique to address the multi-objective optimization problem⁽¹⁴⁾. With this method, a multi-objective optimization issue is reduced to a single objective with weights that reflect the decision maker's priorities between the objectives.

This paper uses makespan, total cost and resource utilization for formulate the objective fitness function. An essential component in task scheduling is makespan, defined as the total processing time for all tasks over a specified collection of virtual machines. This is expressed by **Eq. (1)**.

$$F1(Makespan) = Max(CPT(v_i)), \quad \forall i \in 1, 2, \dots, m \tag{1}$$

where CPT represents the complete processing time of ith VM and it can be computed as,

$$CPT(v_i) = \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{TaskLength(t_j)}{MIPS(v_i)} \tag{2}$$

where TaskLength(t_j) denotes the length of the jth task, quantified by the number of instructions (in millions). MIPS(v_i) signifies the processing efficiency of the ith virtual machine measured in millions of instructions per second.

The next objective is total cost which can be computed as,

$$F2(TotalCost) = \sum_{i=1}^m cost_i \times CPT(v_i) \tag{3}$$

Where $cost_i$ represents the i^{th} vm unit cost.

The last objective is resource utilization (RU). It is a metric for calculating resource consumption. Elevated utilization signifies that the cloud provider achieves optimal profitability. It can be computed using,

$$F3(RU) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m CPT(v_i)}{Makespan \times m} \tag{4}$$

The fitness function is established by computing a weighted mean of each individual fitness function. The proposed fitness function (F) is presented in Eq. (5),

$$F = (F1) + (F2) + (1 - F3) \tag{5}$$

The minimal value of the fitness function yields an optimal solution

2.1 Proposed MSOA Task Scheduling

This section elucidates the proposed modified version of the Sunflower Optimization Algorithm. Figure 1 shows the general architecture of proposed approach.

Fig 1. Proposed Architecture

The Sunflower Optimization Algorithm (SOA) is a nature-inspired algorithm introduced by G.F. Gomes et al. (21). The algorithm emulates the pollination process between the two closest sunflowers while moving towards the sun. The SOA consists

of two parts: pollination and movement. During the pollination, sunflowers collaborate to generate pollen gametes. During the movement, sunflowers randomly advance towards the optimal sunflower, seen as the sun. The typical SOA algorithm exhibits slow convergence and is prone to entrapment in local minima. This work offers a modified sunflower optimization algorithm (MSOA) using Lévy flight, mutation, and crossover operations to enhance diversity search in the traditional SOA. The Lévy flight operator is a stochastic walking technique that assists the SOA in evading entrapment in local minima and preventing early convergence.

Algorithm 1 explains the Pseudo-code for the MSOA task scheduling algorithm.

Algorithm-1 MSOA Task Scheduling **Input:** m virtual machines ($V = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_m\}$), n tasks ($T = \{t_1, t_2, t_3, \dots, t_n\}$)
Output: Optimal Allocation of Tasks to VMs, Makespan, Cost, Resource Utilization
 Step01: Initialize parameters : population size, maximum number of iterations (maxIter)
 Step02: Randomly generate the initial population using Eq. (7)
 Step03: Compute fitness for initial population using Eq. (5)
 Step04: Find the minimum fitness value and assign to bestSolution
 Step05: Set $iter = 0$
 Step06: While ($iter < maxIter$) do
 Step07: Select two populations which has highest fitness value.
 Step08: Apply Crossover operation
 Step09: Apply Mutation operation
 Step10: Update population using Levy Flight operation using Eq. (8)
 Step11: Compute the fitness for newly updated population using Eq. (5)
 Step12: Update the bestSolution
 Step13: $iter = iter + 1$
 Step14: End While
 Step15: Return the bestSolution

The steps of the proposed MSOA algorithm are summarized as follows. The initial parameter values are established, including population size N , maximum iteration number $maxIter$, mutation rate, and Lévy distribution rate. The initial population consists of N number of solutions.

$$Pop = \{P_1, P_2, \dots, P_N\} \tag{6}$$

Each population $P_i = \{P_{i,1}, P_{i,2}, \dots, P_{i,n}\}$ in the population comprises n tasks, each representing the identifier of a VM on which the tasks are executed. Solutions within the population are generated randomly according to the following equation.

$$P_{ij} = rand(1, m) \tag{7}$$

Consider seven tasks $\{t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4, t_5, t_6, t_7\}$ and three virtual machines. A potential solution is $P_i = [1, 2, 1, 3, 1, 2, 3]$, which allocates tasks t_1, t_3 , and t_5 to the first VM, tasks t_2 and t_6 to the second VM, and tasks t_4 and t_7 to the third VM. Two restrictions should be maintained in the task assignment procedure. Each task must be included in the scheduling process, and no task may appear more than once. Considering that task scheduling is a discrete challenge, the indices of tasks and virtual machines are positive integers.

The fitness function for each solution is computed using equation (5). The global best solution is identified, while the least effective solutions are eliminated from the population and substituted with new solutions through crossover and mutation. Crossover and mutation are genetic operators employed to alter the chromosomes of a population. Various types of crossover procedures exist, including single-point, multi-point, and uniform. This article employs a single-point crossover procedure. Two parents from the current population exhibiting superior fitness values are chosen for the crossover operation. A random crossover point is chosen, and the tails of the two progenitors are exchanged to produce new offspring. Figure 2 is an example of a single-point crossover operation.

Mutation can be characterized as a minor random alteration in the chromosome, resulting in a new solution. Mutation can enhance the local search efficacy of an algorithm and preserve the variety of the population. This study employs swap mutation. Randomly select two points on the chromosome and exchange their values. Figure 3 illustrates an example of swap mutation.

Fig 2. Single Point Crossover Operation

Fig 3. Swap Mutation Operation

The solutions are updated utilizing the Lévy flight operator to prevent entrapment in local minima and premature convergence, as described by the following equation.

$$Ly(u) = \left(\frac{\sin(\pi u)}{1} \right)^2 \quad (8)$$

The fitness value for each new solution in the population is computed, and the optimal solution is updated. This procedure is reiterated until the maximum number of iterations is attained. Figure 4 shows the workflow of modified sunflower optimization algorithm.

3 Results and Discussion

This section presents the experimental outcomes of allocating different tasks over a differing number of virtual machines. The outcomes of the proposed MSOA are compared with those achieved by the standard SOA and PSO regarding makespan, cost, and resource utilization. A cloud computing environment tool cloudSim is used to execute the simulation. For simulation, tasks and VMs range from 100 to 500 and 10 to 50. The length of the task is 1000 to 5000 MI, and for VM, it is 500 to 4000 MIPS. The population number, mutation rate, levy, and maximum iteration are 10, 0.1, 1.5, and 150, respectively.

3.1 Evaluation Metrics

The following evaluation metrics are used to assess the performance of the proposed approach: makespan, cost, and resource utilization.

Makespan is a vital scheduling aim in cloud computing, especially for task scheduling. It denotes the cumulative duration required to finalize the execution of a series of tasks within a computing system. Reducing makespan is a prevalent objective in scheduling algorithms, as it directly influences the system’s efficiency and performance. It denotes the total duration necessary to complete a series of actions, and lowering makespan is advantageous for enhancing system efficiency. The makespan is computed using eq. (1).

Cost pertains to the economic factors related to the distribution and utilization of resources in a cloud environment. Reducing costs is essential for both service providers and customers, since it directly influences the economic effectiveness and affordability of cloud services. The principal objective of cost minimization in cloud scheduling is to deliver economical solutions for customers while maintaining revenue for service providers. The cost is computed using eq. (3).

Fig 4. Workflow of proposed approach

Resource utilization refers to the effective and efficient employment of all available resources. A high usage value indicates that the cloud provider achieves optimal profitability. It can be computed using eq. (4).

3.2 Result Analysis

The proposed technique evaluates two scenarios: Investigating the impact of altering task quantities from 100 to 500 while maintaining a constant virtual machine count of 20. Examining the impact of different VM numbers ranging from 10 to 50 while maintaining a constant task count of 400. The performance parameters of makespan, cost, and resource utilization are assessed for both scenarios.

When the number of tasks is changed and the number of virtual machines is set at 20, the following outcomes are observed:

Table 2 presents a comparison of makespan for varying quantities of tasks. As the quantity of tasks escalates, the makespan correspondingly rises. The task scheduling based on PSO and SOA exhibits greater makespan values compared to MSOA. The

execution duration of each activity fluctuates according on the virtual machine’s capacity, resulting in a makespan that changes according to the several methodologies utilized. The proposed approach demonstrates superior outcomes and has the lowest makespan compared to the other two conventional methods.

Table 2. Makespan Comparison (Fixed VM and Varying Task)

No of Tasks	Makespan (Sec.)		
	PSO	SOA	MSOA
100	10.13	9.34	5.73
200	29.10	25.56	19.73
300	45.43	40.19	33.27
400	62.56	59.50	50.13
500	90.42	82.13	75.46

Figure 5 illustrates the graphical comparison of performance metrics fixed VMs over varying tasks.

Fig 5. Performance metric comparison for fixed VM and varying No. of tasks

Table 3 illustrates the impact of an increased number of tasks on processing costs. The execution time of each activity fluctuates based on the virtual machine’s capability, resulting in variable costs contingent upon the approaches utilized. It has been noted that an increase in the number of tasks correlates with a rise in processing costs. The comparison findings indicate that the proposed method produced the most cost-effective optimal scheduling solution.

Table 4 presents a comparison of utilization of resources. The proposed MSOA enhances utilization of resources relative to alternative methods.

The subsequent results are presented after altering the quantity of virtual machines and configuring the task count to 400.

Table 3. Cost Comparison (Fixed VM and Varying Task)

No of Tasks	Cost (\$)		
	PSO	SOA	MSOA
100	32.34	30.15	25.17
200	96.03	93.56	87.37
300	140.24	136.01	124.24
400	200.45	194.34	172.53
500	249.39	231.58	205.11

Table 4. Resource Utilization Comparison (Fixed VM and Varying Task)

No of Tasks	Resource Utilization (%)		
	PSO	SOA	MSOA
100	87.34	89.12	95.10
200	94.23	95.24	97.23
300	95.89	97.21	99.01
400	96.34	98.12	99.43
500	97.58	98.42	99.69

Table 5 illustrates the impact of the rising quantity of VMs on makespan. The makespan of 50 VMs for PSO, SOA and MSOA was 32.46, 28.44 and 15.45 seconds respectively.

Table 5. Makespan (Sec.) Comparison (Fixed Task and Varying VM)

No of VMs	Makespan (Sec.)		
	PSO	SOA	MSOA
10	73.18	70.34	66.96
20	62.56	59.50	50.13
30	55.89	50.13	43.85
40	39.09	34.90	28.30
50	32.46	28.44	15.45

Table 6 demonstrates the impact of varying the number of VMs on processing expenses. The cost of 50 VMs for PSO, SOA and MSOA was 290.12, 274.90 and 246.43\$ respectively.

Table 6. Cost (\$) Comparison (Fixed Task and Varying VM)

No of VMs	Cost (\$)		
	PSO	SOA	MSOA
10	185.30	178.32	163.42
20	200.45	194.34	172.53
30	234.89	212.89	188.60
40	269.24	253.81	196.86
50	290.12	274.90	246.43

Table 7 presents a comparison of the utilization of resources. Increasing the number of VMs results in decreased resource use. The resource utilization of 50 VMs for PSO, SOA and MSOA was 91.90%, 93.34% and 97.01% respectively.

Figure 6 illustrates the graphical comparison of performance metrics for fixed tasks over varying quantities of virtual machines (VMs).

The experimental findings indicate that the suggested scheduling method achieved a makespan reduction of up to 22.43%, a cost reduction of 14.47%, and a 3.89% enhancement in resource utilization compared to PSO. The proposed solution

Table 7. Resource Utilization (%) Comparison (Fixed Task and Varying VM)

No of VMs	Resource Utilization (%)		
	PSO	SOA	MSOA
10	97.54	98.89	99.78
20	96.34	98.12	99.43
30	95.98	97.23	98.81
40	94.12	95.48	97.53
50	91.90	93.34	97.01

Fig 6. Performance metric comparison for the fixed task and varying No. of VMs

demonstrates a 14.95% reduction in makespan, a 10.38% decrease in cost, and a 2.51% enhancement in resource utilization compared to SOA.

Table 8 presents a comparison of performance metrics for different approaches. Only a few approaches^{(13), (19)} use the sunflower optimization algorithm for the task scheduling problem, which does not consider all 3 parameters (makespan, cost, and resource utilization). The comprehensive results indicate that the suggested methodology surpasses existing approaches in terms of makespan, cost, and resource use, while also demonstrating greater stability and scalability.

4 Conclusion

Task scheduling is a substantial NP-hard challenge in cloud computing, affecting the efficiency and resource usage of cloud datacenters. Effective scheduling is a crucial determinant of enhanced service quality. This work presents the MSOA algorithm

Table 8. Performance metrics comparison

Approach	Metrics		
	Makespan (Sec.)	Cost (\$)	Resource Utilization (%)
ESFO ⁽¹³⁾	58	-	-
ACPSO ⁽¹⁸⁾	35.76	48.74	53.91
OSFO ⁽¹⁹⁾	14.52	45.07	-
Proposed MSOA	5.73	25.17	95.10

for task scheduling, a pivotal issue in cloud computing. The MSOA enhances the traditional SOA algorithm to effectively explore the solution space. The conventional sunflower optimization technique is enhanced with the incorporation of operations like as Lévy flight, crossover, and mutation. It can balance the expansion and intensification processes of the proposed strategy and avert trapping in local minima. The suggested approach identifies an efficient task scheduling solution with polynomial time complexity. The simulation is conducted to evaluate the efficacy of this study endeavor. The simulation test results indicate that the suggested approach reduces makespan time and cost while improving resource utilization compared to existing techniques: PSO and SOA. The proposed approach reduces the average of 22.43% and 14.95%, when compared to the PSO and SOA in terms of makespan, 14.47% and 10.38% of cost reduced compared to PSO and SOA, 3.89% and 2.51% of resource utilization increased compared to other algorithms. Consequently, it can be inferred that the proposed approach enhances task scheduling performance regarding makespan, cost, and resource utilization. The future scope includes:

- To create an enhanced version of the algorithm with parameter tuning.
- To develop a hybrid meta-heuristic approach for efficient task scheduling.
- To incorporate additional performance measures such as response time and energy consumption.
- A substantial volume of real-world data within an authentic cloud environment will be utilized for effective task scheduling.

References

- 1) Konjaang JK, Xu L. Meta-heuristic Approaches for Effective Scheduling in Infrastructure as a Service Cloud: A Systematic Review. *Journal of Network and Systems Management*. 2021 Jan;29(2). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10922-020-09577-2>.
- 2) Alla HB, Alla SB, Ezzati A, Touhafi A. A novel multiclass priority algorithm for task scheduling in cloud computing. *The Journal of Supercomputing*. 2021 Mar;77(10):11514–11555. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11227-021-03741-4>.
- 3) Amer DA, Attiya G, Zeidan I, Nasr AA. Elite learning Harris hawks optimizer for multi-objective task scheduling in cloud computing. *The Journal of Supercomputing*. 2021 Jul;78(2):2793–2818. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11227-021-03977-0>.
- 4) Saravanan T, Ramesh K. A Bio-inspired Energy Efficient Dynamic Task Scheduling (BEDTS) scheme and classification for virtualization CDC. *Journal of Engineering Research [Internet]*. 2023 Aug;12(3):387–396. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jer.2023.08.026>.
- 5) Siddiqi F, Gazi MH, Aslam M. A review of task scheduling in cloud computing based on nature-inspired optimization algorithm. *Cluster Computing*. 2023 Jun;26(5):3037–3067. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10586-023-04090-y>.
- 6) Alhaidari F, Balharith TZ. Enhanced Round-Robin Algorithm in the Cloud Computing Environment for Optimal Task Scheduling. *Computers*. 2021 May;10(5):63. <https://doi.org/10.3390/computers10050063>.
- 7) Toaza B, Esztergár-Kiss D. A review of metaheuristic algorithms for solving TSP-based scheduling optimization problems. *Applied Soft Computing*. 2023 Nov;148:110908. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asoc.2023.110908>.
- 8) Wang Y, Zhao J, Jiang K, Zhou Q, Kang Z, Chen C, et al. Prediction of TBM operation parameters using machine learning models based on BPSO. *Adv Eng Inform*. 2023;56:101955. Available from: <https://dblp.org/rec/journals/aei/WangZJKZCZ23.html>.
- 9) Imene L, Sihem S, Okba K, Mohamed B. A third generation genetic algorithm NSGAIII for task scheduling in cloud computing. *J King Saud Univ Comput Inf Sci*. 2022;34(9):7515–7529. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jksuci.2021.12.007>.
- 10) Nabi S, Ahmad M, Ibrahim M, Hamam H. AdPSO: adaptive PSO-based task scheduling approach for cloud computing. *Sensors (Basel)*. 2022;22(3):920. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22030920>.
- 11) Alsadie D. TSMGWO: Optimizing task schedule using multi-objectives grey wolf optimizer for cloud data centers. *IEEE Access*. 2021;9:37707–37725. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3062610>.
- 12) Sharma N, Garg P. Ant colony based optimization model for QoS-Based task scheduling in cloud computing environment. *Measurement: Sensors*. 2022;24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measen.2022.100531>.
- 13) Emami H. Cloud task scheduling using enhanced sunflower optimization algorithm. *ICT Express*. 2022;8(1):97–100. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.icte.2021.04.008>.
- 14) Kruekaew B, Kimpan W. Multi-objective task scheduling optimization for load balancing in cloud computing environment using hybrid artificial bee colony algorithm with reinforcement learning. *IEEE Access*. 2022;10:17803–17818. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3148871>.
- 15) Behera I, Sobhanayak S. Task scheduling optimization in heterogeneous cloud computing environments: a hybrid GA-GWO approach. *J Parallel Distrib Comput*. 2024;183. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpdc.2023.104766>.
- 16) Ledmi A, Ledmi M, Souidi MEH, Haouassi H, Bardou D. Optimizing task scheduling in cloud computing using discrete tuna swarm optimization. *Ing Syst Inf*. 2024;29(1):323–335. <https://doi.org/10.18280/isi.290132>.

- 17) Pabitha P, Nivitha K, Gunavathi C, Panjavarnam B. A chameleon and remora search optimization algorithm for handling task scheduling uncertainty problem in cloud computing. *Sustain Comput Inform Syst.* 2024;41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.suscom.2023.100944>.
- 18) Dubey K, Sharma SC. A hybrid multi-faceted task scheduling algorithm for cloud computing environment. *International Journal of System Assurance Engineering and Management.* 2023;14(Suppl 3):774–788. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13198-021-01084-0>.
- 19) Chandrashekar C, Krishnadoss P. Opposition based sunflower optimization algorithm using cloud computing environments. *Materials Today: Proceedings.* 2022 Jan;62:4896–4902. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2022.03.534>.
- 20) Abualigah L, Diabat A. A novel hybrid antlion optimization algorithm for multi-objective task scheduling problems in cloud computing environments. *Cluster Comput.* 2021;24(1):205–223. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10586-020-03140-2>.
- 21) Gomes GF, da Cunha SS, Anceletti AC. A sunflower optimization (SFO) algorithm applied to damage identification on laminated composite plates. *Eng Comput.* 2019;35:619–626. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00366-018-0617-5>.